

Nanoparticles: An Overview

M. Balasundaresan*, **S.K. Senthil Kumar¹**, **M. Rahamath Khan**, **V. Rajeshwari**,
K. Ranjani, **R. Ranjith Kumar**, **V. Rohini²**

*Associate Professor, Arunai College Of Pharmacy, Tiruvannamalai – 606 603.

¹ Principal, Arunai College Of Pharmacy, Tiruvannamalai – 606 603.

² B.Pharm Vii Sem Students, Arunai College Of Pharmacy, Tiruvannamalai – 606 603.

ABSTRACT

Nanoparticles (NPs) have emerged as a revolutionary platform in science and technology due to their unique physicochemical, structural, and functional properties at the nanometre scale (1– 100 nm) ⁽²⁾. Nanotechnology is an interdisciplinary subject. A large number of techniques like physical, mechanical, chemical, biological and hybrid are available to synthesize different types of nanomaterials ⁽⁵⁾. Their high surface area-to-volume ratio, tunable size, and ability to be engineered with surface modifications make them highly versatile across multiple fields including medicine, pharmaceuticals, materials science, and environmental applications ⁽²⁾. Recently, nanotechnology is used in bio sensing, drug delivery, nano devices, separation and purification purposes ⁽⁹⁾. The nanoparticles are generally classified into the organic, inorganic and carbon-based particles in nanometric scale that has improved properties compared to larger sizes of respective materials. The nanoparticles show enhanced properties such as high reactivity, strength, surface area, sensitivity, stability, etc. because of their small size ⁽¹¹⁾. This modern form of therapy is especially important when there is a discrepancy between the dose or the concentration of a drug and its therapeutic results or toxic effects. Cell-specific targeting can be accomplished by attaching drugs to specially designed carriers ^[20]. Particulate systems like nanoparticles have been used as a physical approach to alter and improve the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties of various types of drug molecules ⁽¹⁴⁾. This review paper focused on detailed overview of the properties, synthesis, Classification, advantages, disadvantages and application of the nanoparticles (NP) subsist in different forms ⁽⁸⁾.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, Nanotechnology, drug delivery, bio sensing, pharmacokinetic, physical approach and pharmacodynamic properties.

INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is a known field of research since last century. Since “nanotechnology “was presented by Nobel laureate Richard P. Feynman during his well famous 1959 lecture. “There’s Plenty of Room at the Bottom” (Feynman, 1960), there have been made various revolutionary developments in the field of nanotechnology. Nanoparticles are extremely small particles with at least one dimension between 1 and 100nanometers (nm) ^[2]. Nanotechnology is a multidisciplinary subject dealing with nanosized materials and has encountered its profound use in various domains like electronics, chemistry, biotechnology, engineering, and physical and material science. Moreover, nanoscale materials can be a

system or device, or these could be composites, complexes, or supramolecular structures ^[16]. Nanotechnology refers to an emerging field of science that includes synthesis and development of various nanomaterials ^[10]. Nanotechnology is the fascinating branch of science which encompasses study of systems having nano scale size. The prefix ‘nano’ comes from Latin word ‘nanus’ meaning dwarf or tiny. With the convention of International System of Units (SI) it is used to indicate a reduction factor of 10⁹ times (1nm corresponding to 10⁻⁹ m) ^[3]. Nanoparticles are also referred to as “zero-dimensional” nanomaterial. This definition stems from the fact that all of their dimensions are on the nanoscale, as opposed to one-dimensional nanomaterials (such as nanowires and nanotubes) and

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two-dimensional nanomaterials (such as self-assembled monolayer films) [2]. In medication, nanoparticles are utilized to convey drugs for both diagnosing and treating illnesses [4]. Two main factors cause nanomaterials to behave significantly differently than the same materials at larger dimensions: surface effects and quantum effects. Nanomaterials have different surface effects compared to micromaterials or bulk materials, mainly due to three reasons; (a) dispersed nanomaterials have a very large surface area and high particle number per mass unit, (b) the fraction of atoms at the surface in nanomaterials is increased, and (c) the atoms situated at the surface in nanomaterials have fewer direct neighbours [18]. The drug is dissolved, entrapped, encapsulated or attached to a nanoparticle matrix. Depending upon the method of preparation, nanoparticles, nanospheres or nano capsules can be obtained. Nano capsules are systems in which the drug is confined to a cavity surrounded by a unique polymer membrane, while nanospheres are matrix systems in which the drug is physically and uniformly dispersed. In recent years, biodegradable polymeric nanoparticles, particularly those coated with hydrophilic polymer such as poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG) known as long-circulating particles, have been used as potential drug delivery devices because of their ability to circulate for a prolonged period time target a particular organ, as carriers of DNA in gene therapy, and their ability to deliver proteins, peptides and genes [14]. When researchers discovered that size can affect a substance's physio-chemical properties, such as its optical properties, they realised the significance of these materials. Wine red, yellowish grey, black, and dark black are the colours of 20-nm gold (Au), platinum (Pt), silver (Ag), and palladium (Pd) NPs, respectively. NPs are made up of three layers: (a) the surface layer, which can be complexed with a variety of small molecules, metal ions, surfactants, and polymers; and (b) The shell layer, which is chemically and physically distinguishable from the core, and (c) the core, which is the NP's central portion as well as generally refers to the NP itself as shown in Fig. 1. The colour of the solution changes as the aspect ratio, nano shell thickness, and percent gold concentration change, Changes in any of the above-mentioned factors affect the absorption properties of the NP, resulting in different absorption colours [8].

Figure 1: layer of nano particles [8]

CLASSIFICATION: [2, 3]

Nanoparticles (NPs) are mainly classified into various classes based on their morphology, size, physical & chemical properties. They are classified into two categories based on dimensionalities and based on composition.

BASED ON DIMENSIONALITIES:

The key elements of nanotechnology are the nanomaterials. Nanomaterials are defined as materials where at least one of their dimensions is in the nanoscale, i.e. smaller than 100 nm. Based on their dimensionalities, nanomaterials are placed into four different classes.

- ❖ **Zero-dimensional nanomaterials(0-D):** the nanomaterials in this class have all their three dimensions in the nanoscale range. Examples are quantum dots, fullerenes, and nanoparticles.
- ❖ **One-dimensional nanomaterial (1-D):** the nanomaterials in this class have one dimension outside the nanoscale. Examples are nanotubes, nanofibers, Nano rods, nanowires, and Nano horns.
- ❖ **Two-dimensional nanomaterials(2-D):** the nanomaterials in this class have two dimensions outside the nanoscale. Examples are Nano sheets, nanofilms, and Nano layers.
- ❖ **Three-dimensional nanomaterials (3-D) or bulk nanomaterials:** in this class the

materials are not confined to the nanoscale in any dimension. This class contain bulk

powders, dispersions of nanoparticles, arrays of nanowires and nanotubes.

Figure 2: Classification of nanoparticles.

BASED ON COMPOSITION: [3, 2, 6, 7, 11]

Nanoparticles (NPs) are mainly classified into various classes based on their morphology, size, physical & chemical properties. They are mainly classified into organic, inorganic and carbon-based NPs.

❖ **Organic Nanoparticles:** This class comprises NPs that are made of proteins, carbohydrates, lipids, polymers, or any other organic compounds. Organic nanoparticles are the solid particles composed of organic compounds such as lipids or polymers with a diameter in the range of 10 nm to 1 μ m. Dendrimers, micelles, liposomes and ferritin, etc. are commonly known as the organic nanoparticles or polymers as shown in figure 3. Organic NPs are sensitive to thermal and electromagnetic radiation such as heat and light. In addition, they are often formed by noncovalent intermolecular interactions, which make them more labile in nature and offer a route for clearance from the body. There are different parameters that determine the potential field of application of organic NPs, e.g., composition, surface morphology, stability, carrying capacity etc. Today, organic NPs are mostly used in the biomedical field in targeted drug delivery and cancer therapy. Both micelles and liposomes have a hollow core also known as nano capsules and

are sensitive to thermal and electromagnetic radiations. These unique properties make organic NPs an ideal choice for drug delivery. They are highly efficient in target drug delivery.

Figure 3 Organic nanoparticles: a) Dendrimers, b) Liposomes and c) micelles.

❖ **Inorganic nanoparticles:** Inorganic nanoparticles are the particles that are not made of carbon. It includes metal and metal oxides. Depending on atomic packing, they can exhibit diverse shapes—including spheres, cylinders, ellipsoids, cubes, oblate forms, and stars—while retaining the crystallinity of metal-based compounds. The typical examples of this class are metal, ceramic, and semiconductor NPs. Metal NPs are purely made of metal precursors, they can be monometallic, bimetallic, or polymetallic, Bimetallic NPs can be made from alloys or

formed in different layers (core-shell). These unique properties make organic NPs an ideal choice for drug delivery. They are highly efficient in target drug delivery.

1. **Metal based nanoparticles:**

Metal based nanoparticles can be obtained from metals such as aluminium (Al), gold (Au), silver (Ag), cadmium (Cd), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), iron (Fe), lead (Pb) and zinc (Zn). The most widely used metals in are Ag, Au, Cu, Fe and Zn. Transition metals are found to be the best candidates for the synthesis of metal-based NPs due to the presence of partially filled d- orbitals which make them more redox active. High reactivity and sensitivity to environmental factors such as air, moisture, heat, sunlight etc [3].

- **Gold based nanoparticles:** Gold nanoparticles are nanometre-sized particles with unique physical and chemical properties that enable them to absorb and scatter visible as well as near-infrared light. They are considered highly stable, non-toxic, and easy to synthesize. Owing to their remarkable characteristics—such as the quantum size effect and the ability to assemble into diverse structures—gold nanoparticles serve as excellent model systems for scientific research [6].
- **Silver nanoparticles:** The unique physicochemical properties of silver nanoparticles—such as electrical and thermal conductivity, catalytic activity, and non-linear optical behaviour—have led to the development of numerous innovative products and scientific applications [6].
- **Iron oxide nanoparticles:** Iron (III) oxide (Fe₂O₃) is a reddish brown, inorganic compound which is paramagnetic in nature and also one of the three main oxides of iron, while other two being Fe_o and Fe₃O₄. The Fe₃O₄, which also occurs naturally as the mineral magnetite, is super paramagnetic in nature. Due to their ultrafine size, magnetic properties, and biocompatibility, super paramagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) have emerged as promising

candidates for various biomedical applications, such as enhanced resolution contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), targeted drug delivery and imaging, hyperthermia, gene therapy, stem cell tracking, molecular/cellular tracking, magnetic separation technologies (e. g., rapid DNA sequencing) for early detection of inflammatory, cancer, diabetes, and atherosclerosis [12].

- **Copper nanoparticles:** Cu is an element of 3d transition metal and has some unique physical and chemical properties. Cu possess wide range of oxidation states (Cu⁰, Cu^I, Cu^{II}, Cu^{III}) i.e. Cu-based material undergo wide range of reactions Due to its low cost and admirable electrical conductivity the demand of Cu nanoparticle is increase in the field of electric circuit [15]. Cu nanoparticles have various applications in the field of water treatment, catalysts and solar cell [13].

1. **METAL OXIDES BASED NANOPARTICLES:**

Metal based NPs can be converted into their corresponding oxides known as metal oxides-based NPs. Metal oxides-based NPs have exceptional properties as compared with their metal counterparts. Some examples of metal oxides-based NPs are Iron oxide (Fe₂O₃), Magnetite (Fe₃O₄), Aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃), Cerium oxide (CeO₂), Silicon dioxide (SiO₂), Titanium oxide (TiO₂), Zinc oxide (ZnO) These metal oxides-based NPs found to be more reactive and efficient [3].

- **Zinc oxide nanoparticles:** ZnO nanoparticles are safe and biocompatible, making them ideal for use in textiles and surfaces that contact human skin. They exhibit antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as well as heat- and pressure-resistant spores [6].
- **Titanium oxide nanoparticles:** The antimicrobial activity of TiO₂ nanoparticles is influenced by their crystal structure, shape, and size. TiO₂ NPs are particularly responsive to oxidative stress due to the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). They have been shown to

enhance the effectiveness of antibiotics—such as beta-lactams, cephalosporins, aminoglycosides, lincosamides, and tetracyclines—against MRSA [6].

- **Carbon Based Nanoparticles:** The nanoparticles composed of carbon are known as carbon-based NPs. Carbon based NPs can exist in different shapes such as tube-shaped, horn-shaped, spherical or ellipsoidal. Two major classes of carbon-based NPs are fullerene and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) as shown in figure 4. Other classes of carbon-based NPs are graphene, nano fibres, carbon black [3]. Carbon materials are synthesized using three techniques: chemical

vapor deposition, laser ablation, and arch discharge [6]. Carbon nanostructured possess a unique hybridization properties and sensitivity to perturbation during synthesis as a result of which fine manipulation take place in mechanical properties. Carbon nanostructured possess unique such as electrical, mechanical and structure diversity and has been used in various biological application including drug delivery, tissue engineering, bio sensing, imaging, diagnosis and cancer treatment [13].

Figure 4. Carbon based nanoparticles: a – fullerenes, b – graphene, c – carbon nanotubes, d – carbon nanofibers and e – carbon black

1. Fullerene:

Nobel laureates H. W. Kroto, R. F. Curl and R. E. Smalley discovered fullerenes in the year 1985. The fullerene family includes a number of atomic clusters (C_n) where n > 20. Fullerene C₆₀ is the most common fullerene having 60 carbon atoms. It is also known as bucky ball [3]. Fullerenes are spherical carbon nanoparticles formed through Sp² hybridization. The process produces round, mono-layered fullerenes up to 8.3 nm and poly-layered fullerenes with diameters ranging from 4-36 nm [6]. About 28 to 1500 carbon atoms form the spherical structure with diameters up to 8.2 nm for a single layer and 4 to 36 nm for multi-layered fullerenes [11]. Fullerenes are also used to

construct biosensor because it exhibits good biocompatibility, low background current, high chemical stability, high carrier capacity etc. [13]. It has the shape of a soccer ball due to the cage-like arrangement of its 60 carbon atoms, each of which has three bonds. Twelve pentagons and twenty hexagons are utilized in the C₆₀ structure. Two well-established characteristics of this structure are resonance stabilization and icosahedral symmetry [17].

2. Graphene:

Graphene is another allotropic form of carbon. It has a two-dimensional honeycomb like lattice. Graphene sheet is generally 1 nm in thickness [3, 11]. Diameters ranging from micro to millimetres. This material features high intrinsic strength, thermal conductivity,

biocompatibility, and low toxicity. The most significant benefits for biosensing [6].

3. Carbon nanotube:

Iizima was discovered the first to find the carbon nanotube in 1991. Single-walled carbon nanotubes and multiwalled carbon nanotubes are two types of carbon nanotubes [13]. Carbon Nano Tubes (CNTs) are made of graphene nano foil with a honeycomb Lattice of carbon atoms twisted into hollow cylinders. The length of the nanotubes can vary from a few micrometres to 100 nm, with diameters as low as 0.7 nm for single-layered CNTs and 100 nm for multi-layered CNTs. Too Many millimetres. A half-fullerene molecule can shut the ends or leave them hollow [17]. The ends can either be hollow or closed by a half fullerene molecule [11].

4. Carbon nano fibre:

Carbon nanofibers (CNFs) are also made up of graphene sheets. In this graphene layers are arranged as stacked cones, cups or plates [3]. CNT but wound into a cone or cup shape instead of a regular cylindrical tube [11]. CNFs have excellent mechanical properties, high thermal and electrical conductivity. Their diameter varies form 10 nm to 500 nm. Hence, these CNFs find application in many fields such as drug delivery, energy devices, sensors, nanocomposites, photocatalysis etc [3]. CNTs have high specific surface area and oleophilic characteristics, making them ideal for developing an oil removing membrane with high penetration flux [30, 6].

5. Carbon black:

Carbon black nanoparticles (CBNP) or nano powders are amorphous materials mainly composed of elemental carbon. It is also known as 'soot' or 'shouen. These generally find application in laser printing, copy machine inks. They are also used as rubber reinforcement preservatives as well as pigments in plastic industries [3]. An amorphous material made up of carbon, generally spherical in shape with diameters from 20 to 70 nm. The interactions between the particles are so high that they bound in aggregates and around 500 nm agglomerates are formed.

ADVANTAGES: [1, 17, 21, 25, 26]

1. Enhancement of solubility and bioavailability.
2. Enhancement of pharmacological activity.
3. Sustained drug delivery.
4. Protection from degradation.
5. Enhancement of permeability.
6. Decreased side effects compared to conventional drug delivery.
7. Improved therapeutic effect.
8. Nanoparticles can better distribute drugs to small areas inside the body.
9. The other ways to administer the system, such as parenteral, nasal, and oral.
10. Drug transportation through cell barriers gets easier.
11. Smaller dose form.
12. Smaller drug dose less toxicity.
13. It offers targeted delivery of drug.
14. It increases drug resistance time.
15. Proportionality of dose.
16. Lower dosages of drugs have less toxicity.
17. Both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drug can be easily delivered.
18. Tumour targeting using Nanoparticulate delivery system.
19. Nanoparticles for oral delivery of peptides and proteins.
20. Nanoparticles for Gene delivery.

DISADVANTAGES: [6, 17, 21, 25, 26]

1. Nanoparticles 'small size and large surface area make them extremely reactive in the cellular environment.
2. Non-biodegradable particles can collect at drug delivery sites, leading to chronic inflammation.
3. Nanoparticles have limited targeting capabilities, making it unable to terminate the therapy.
4. Nanoparticles exhibit strong reactivity due to their small size and large surface area.
5. It entails higher production costs, which can drive up the price of formulation.
6. When they show through to the cell dermis.
7. Unpredictable gelation tendency.
8. More complex operational procedure.
9. Higher chances of contamination.
10. Handling of nanoparticles are very difficult in their liquid and dry forms due to smaller size and larger surface area.
11. The cost of manufacture is high and encapsulation efficiency is less.
12. The solvent system used during the preparation process may produce toxicity.
13. Leakage and sudden release of the drug may be one of the critical problems.

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS:

1. The size, surface characteristics and shape of a nano particle has a key role in its biodistribution in vivo. The effects of size have been studied extensively with spherically shaped particles and some general trends have been noted.
2. Particles less than 5 nm are rapidly cleared from the circulation through extravasation or renal clearance.

3. Particle size increases from the nanometre range to ~15 µm, accumulation occurs primarily in the liver, the spleen and the bone marrow.
4. Nanoparticle behaviour in the size range ~10 nm to ~15 µm varies widely in terms of biodistribution, and cellular uptake of nanoparticles in this range is heavily dependent on cell type [19].

PHARMACEUTICAL ASPECTS OF NANOPARTICLES:

Nano-particles in the point of view, three important process parameters are performed before releasing them for clinical-trials.

1. Purification of Nanoparticles: A new methodology known as "cross flow filtration method" has been used and suggested for the purification of nanoparticles. In these methods nanoparticles suspension is filtered through membrane with direction of fluid being tangential to the surface of the membranes used.
2. Freeze drying of Nano-particles: This technique involves freezing of nanoparticle suspension sublimation of its water content under reduced pressure to get a free-flowing powdered material.
3. Sterilization of Nano-particles: Nanoparticles intended for parenteral use should be sterilized product be pyrogen free. Filtration through 0.22micron membrane cannot produce a complete sterilized product. Sterilization in case of nanoparticles is best achieved by using aseptic technique throughout their preparation and formulation and or by subsequent sterilizing treatment like autoclaving or irradiation [21].

METHOD OF SYNTHESIS OF NANOPARTICLES

The nanoparticles are synthesised by various methods that are categorised into bottom-up or top-down method [11].

Bottom-Up Method:

The bottom-up or constructive approach involves assembling materials from atoms or molecules into clusters and ultimately into nanoparticles. This method allows precise control over particle size,

shape, and composition. Some of the most widely used bottom-up techniques for nanoparticle synthesis include:

1. Sol-gel method

2. Chemical vapor deposition (CVD)

3. Pyrolysis

4. Electrospinning

Figure 5. Synthesis process

1. Sol-gel method:

The sol- a colloidal solution of solids suspended in a liquid phase. The gel- a solid macromolecule submerged in a solvent. Sol-gel is the most preferred bottom-up method due to its simplicity and as most of the nanoparticles can be synthesised from this method. It is a wet-chemical process containing a chemical solution acting as a precursor

for an integrated system of discrete particle. Metal oxides and chlorides are the typically used precursors in sol-gel process. The precursor is then dispersed in a host liquid either by shaking, stirring or sonication and the resultant system contains a liquid and a solid phase. A phase separation is carried out to recover the nanoparticles by various methods such as sedimentation, filtration and centrifugation and the moisture is further removed by drying^[11].

Figure 6. Sol-gel method.

2. Chemical vapor deposition (CVD):

Chemical vapour deposition is the deposition of a thin film of gaseous reactants onto a substrate. The deposition is carried out in a reaction chamber at ambient temperature by combining gas molecules. A chemical reaction occurs when a heated substrate comes in contact with the combined gas. This reaction produces a thin film of product on the substrate

surface that is recovered and used. Substrate temperature is the influencing factor in CVD. The advantages of CVD are highly pure, uniform, hard and strong nanoparticles. The disadvantages of CVD are the requirement of special equipment and the gaseous by-products are highly toxic [11].

Figure 7. Chemical vapour deposition

3. Pyrolysis:

Pyrolysis is the most commonly used process in industries for largescale production of nanoparticle. It involves burning a precursor with flame. The precursor is either liquid or vapour that is fed into the furnace at high pressure through a small hole where it burns. The combustion or by-product gases are then

air classified to recover the nanoparticles. Some of the furnaces use laser and plasma instead of flame to produce high temperature for easy evaporation. The advantages of pyrolysis are simple, efficient, cost effective and continuous process with high yield [7].

Figure 8. Pyrolysis

4. Electrospinning: (Spin Coating / Spinning Disc Reactor (SDR) Method):

The synthesis of nanoparticles by spinning is carried out by a spinning disc reactor (SDR). It contains a rotating disc inside a chamber/reactor where the physical parameters such as temperature can be controlled. The reactor is generally filled with nitrogen or other inert gases to remove oxygen inside and avoid chemical reactions [7]. The disc is rotated at

different speed where the liquid i.e. precursor and water are pumped in. The spinning causes the atoms or molecules to fuse together and is precipitated, collected and dried [11]. The various operating parameters such as the liquid flow rate, disc rotation speed, liquid/precursor ratio, location of feed, disc surface, etc. determines the characteristics nanoparticles synthesised from SDR [9].

Figure 9. Electrospinning

TOP-DOWN METHOD:

Top-down or destructive method is the reduction of a bulk material to nanometric scale particles. Mechanical milling, nanolithography, laser ablation, sputtering and thermal decomposition are some of the most widely used nanoparticle synthesis methods [6].

1. Thermal decomposition method
2. Lithography
3. Laser ablation
4. Sputtering
5. Mechanical milling

1. Thermal decomposition method:

Thermal decomposition. Thermal decomposition is an endothermic chemical decomposition produced by heat that breaks the

chemical bonds in the compound [6]. The specific temperature at which an element chemically decomposes is the decomposition temperature. The nanoparticles are produced by decomposing the metal at specific temperatures undergoing a chemical reaction producing secondary products. Table 1 lists some of the nanoparticles synthesised from these methods [11].

2. Lithography:

Top-down lithographic techniques, either alone or in combination with other fabrication methods such as reactive ion etching (RIE), are widely employed to produce nanoparticles with controlled size and shape. Photolithography, a conventional top-down approach, has been extensively developed for the semiconductor industry and other applications requiring precise micro- and nano-patterns. Ion beam and electron-beam (e beam) lithography enable direct writing of ultra-small structures with extremely fine patterns, as well as the creation of masks or Molds for use in other lithographic processes. However, these techniques are

limited by low throughput and high cost. Nanoimprint lithography (NIL) addresses these limitations by replicating nanostructures from a master Mold in a simple, parallel, and cost-effective manner, providing an efficient solution for top-down nanoparticle fabrication [11].

3. Laser ablation:

Laser ablation. Laser Ablation Synthesis in Solution (LASiS) is a common method for nanoparticle production from various solvents. The irradiation of a metal submerged in a liquid solution by a laser beam condenses a plasma plume that produces nanoparticles [11]. It is a reliable top-down method that provides an alternative solution to conventional chemical reduction of metals to

synthesis metal-based nanoparticles. As LASiS provides a stable synthesis of nanoparticles in organic solvents and water that does not require any stabilising agent or chemicals it is a 'green' process [9].

4. Sputtering:

Sputtering. Sputtering is the deposition of nanoparticles on a surface by ejecting particles from it by colliding with ions. Sputtering is usually a deposition of thin layer of nanoparticles followed by annealing. The thickness of the layer, temperature and duration of annealing, substrate type, etc. determines the shape and size of the nanoparticles [11].

Figure 10. Sputtering

5. Mechanical milling:

Among the various top-down methods, mechanical milling is the most extensively used to produce various nanoparticles. The mechanical milling is used for milling and post annealing of nanoparticles during

synthesis where different elements are milled in an inert atmosphere. The influencing factors in mechanical milling is plastic deformation that leads to particle shape, fracture leads to decrease in particle size and cold-welding leads to increase in particle size [11].

Figure 11. Mechanical milling

APPLICATION OF NANOPARTICLES:

- ❖ Nanoparticles exhibit unique physical and chemical properties such as: electronic and optical properties, mechanical properties, magnetic properties & thermal properties. This uniqueness has led to its application in different areas. Some of the significant applications of NPs are discussed below.
- ❖ Nanoparticles are utilized in showcases to make them more practical, bigger, more splendid, and more productive.
- ❖ They're likewise utilized in elite execution sun-powered cells to produce sustainable power and as antibacterial coatings on wraps.
- ❖ Nanoparticles assist with working on the effectiveness of coolants in transformers and are utilized in enemy of reflection coatings and light-based sensors for disease finding. Also, they're utilized to upgrade the effectiveness of coolants in transformer.
- ❖ Due to some of the properties of nanoparticles and size of nanoparticles, they are used in composite materials and as inorganic filler such as carbon black or silica nanoparticles and nanocomposites. Nanocomposites were employed in the development and design of new materials.
- ❖ As an example, it can be used as the building blocks for new dielectric insulating and magnetic materials. In case of polymers to improve their strength and impact resistance
- ❖ Considering the unique properties discussed in Section 5, NP can be used in variety of applications. Some important of these are given below.
- ❖ Applications in Mechanical Industries.
- ❖ Applications in Energy Harvesting.
- ❖ Applications in electronics.
- ❖ Applications in the environment.
- ❖ Applications in Manufacturing and Materials.
- ❖ Applications in Drugs and Medication.

IN MEDICINE: [9]

- ❖ Cellular imaging
- ❖ In drugs and gene delivery
- ❖ In biological detection of pathogens
- ❖ In probing of the DNA structures
- ❖ By using many kinds of biosensor that are based on NPs diagnosis of different disease

IN FOOD AND AGRICULTURAL: ^[9]

- ❖ For water filtration and desalination
- ❖ For food preservation
- ❖ Production of airtight plastic for packaging of foods.
- ❖ Genetic modification of crop plant can be made.

IN ENERGY HARVESTING: ^[9]

- ❖ Solar cells generation.
- ❖ Water splitting.

APPLICATION OF NANOPARTICLES IN MEDICINE: ^[7]

- ❖ Since nanoparticles are the fundamental building block of nano-biomaterials, nanotechnology raises attention among scientists and researchers in the medical and therapeutic field.

USES OF NANOPARTICLES IN MEDICATION DELIVERY: ^[7]

- ❖ One of the main challenges in the treatment of many diseases is getting the therapeutic component to the desired place.

NANOPARTICLES ARE TARGETED BY ANTIBODIES: ^[7]

- ❖ Numerous studies have shown the use of nanoparticles medicated by antibodies to create tailored drug delivery system, particularly in the context of cancer treatment.

COSMETICS AND SUNSCREEN: ^[11]

- ❖ The conventional ultraviolet [UV] protection sunscreen lacks long-term stability during usage.

CONCLUSION:

In this review article we have given a brief overview of nanoparticles, their structure, classification, method of synthesis, and applications in various fields. Owing to tunable physicochemical as well as biological properties, nanoparticles have gained prominence in medicine, environmental remediation, energy harvesting and many other areas ^[3]. In the pharmaceutical sector, nanoparticles enable targeted and controlled drug release, improving bioavailability and minimizing side effects. Despite their immense potential, challenges such as large-scale production, toxicity concerns, regulatory issues, and stability must be addressed for safe and sustainable applications ^[2].

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